

Fig. 1. D.T.A. of Basic Magnesium Carbonates $4\text{MgCO}_3 \cdot \text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

have a very different thermal behaviour as compared to the pure sample (Curve No. 1). Further, it may be noted that 2% NaCl (corresponding to

TABLE I—COMPOSITION OF LIGHT BASIC MAGNESIUM CARBONATE SAMPLES

Content (%)	1	2	3	4*
MgO	42.50	42.31	42.50	42.35
CO ₂	36.75	36.65	37.20	37.30
Cl	0.05	0.03	0.53	0.06

* Washed with warm water.

about 1% chloride ions) produces the same effect as 0.2% MgCl₂ (corresponding to only 0.14% chloride ions). However, the sample containing 0.2% NaCl

shows three distinct endotherms but no exothermic effect.

Berg¹² obtained similar results during his studies on dolomites and found that the decomposition temperatures were considerably lowered in presence of alkali metal salts. In fact addition of sodium chloride actually changed the ratio of the areas in the d.t.a. within wide limits. The appearance of exotherms thereby reflects on the absence of ionic impurities.

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References

1. S. CALLEBE, *Bull. soc. franc. mineral.*, 1943, **66**, 55.
2. C. W. BECK, cited in "Differential Thermal Analysis", (Ed.) R. C. Mackenzie, Academic Press, London, 1970, Vol. 1, p. 314.
3. C. W. BECK, *Amer. Miner.*, 1950, **35**, 985.
4. J. A. MURRE and H. C. FISCHER, *Proc. Amer. Soc. Test Mater.*, 1951, **51**, 1197.
5. V. SLIZYS and J. KAPACUSKAS, *Lietuvos TSR Mokslu Akad. Darbai*, Ser B, 1958, No. 4, 107; *Chem. Abs.*, **54**, 25686.
6. B. P. CHOUDHARI, M. C. VAIDYA and D. S. DATAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 731.
7. CONST. GH. MACAROVICI and DAN MACAROVICI, *Akad. Rep. Populare Romine, Filiala Oluj. Studii Cercetarii Chim.*, 1960, **11**, 281; *Chem. Abs.*, **57**, 8160.
8. R. M. DELL and S. W. WELLER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1959, **55**, 2203.
9. C. N. R. RAO, S. R. YOGANARSIMHAN and M. P. LEWIS, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1960, **38**, 2359.
10. A. S. SOLEIMANOV, *Trudy Pervogo Saveshchaniyapo Termografi Kazan*, 1953 (Moscow-Leningrad: *Akad. Nauk S.S.S.R.*), 200; *Chem. Abs.*, **53**, 7748.
11. T. L. WEBB cited in "Differential Thermal Analysis", (Ed.) R. C. Mackenzie, Academic Press, London, 1970, Vol. 1, p. 314.
12. L. G. BERG, *Compt. rend. acad. sci. U.R.S.S.*, 1943, **38**, 24; *Chem. Abs.*, **38**, 13.

Derivatization of aliphatic amines as benzylthiuronium dithiocarbamates

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THE derivatization of amines as benzylthiuronium dithiocarbamates¹ was reported as a valuable procedure. The procedure requires the preparation of an almost neutral solution of an ammonium dithiocarbamate. The preparation of such a solution is a bit inconvenient because the dithiocarbamic acids tend to decompose if the pH falls below 7 and if the pH is above 7 the derivative is contaminated by the

TABLE 1—BENZYLTHIURONIUM DITHIOCARBAMATES

Amine	Cor., m.p. of Salts	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		% Nitrogen	
		Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
Ethanolamine	96	43.57	43.26	5.61	6.07	13.87	14.12
3-Propanolamine	91	45.42	45.78	5.99	5.81	13.24	13.30
Diethylamine	100	49.52	49.98	6.67	6.43	13.33	14.10

extensive decomposition of the liberated benzylisothiurea. In an essentially nonaqueous medium, the reaction of aliphatic amines with carbon disulfide to form dithiocarbamic acids² is approximately 90 to 95% complete. By using benzylthiuronium bicarbonate³ instead of benzylthiuronium chloride, the derivatization of aliphatic amines based on the following reaction can, therefore, be carried out with convenience.

The reagent has been observed to have a tendency to decompose at room temperature, however, a well dried sample is stable if stored in a refrigerator. The modified procedure does not require the adjustment of pH and affords better yields because the solid reagent is added till all the dithiocarbamic acid has reacted and the effervescence ceases. The modified procedure was tested in the case of all the aliphatic amines the derivatization of which was reported¹ earlier, the melting points of the derivatives thus obtained agree well with the reported values¹. The data regarding three more aliphatic amines, which have been derivatized now, is furnished in Table 1.

Experimental

Preparation of Benzylthiuronium Dithiocarbamates. In a 10 ml conical flask, 5 drops of an amine, 2 ml of ethanol and 0.5 ml of carbon disulfide are taken. The mixture is swirled for a few minutes and the reagent is added intermittently till the effervescence ceases. Benzylthiuronium dithiocarbamates precipitate at room temperature in most cases, however, in some cases, refrigeration is necessary. The

precipitate is collected by suction filtration. Recrystallization from ethanol affords pure products. Prolonged heating during recrystallization should be avoided because it causes partial decomposition. The derivatives are dried in a vacuum desiccator and the melting points determined by the capillary tube method.

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References

1. N. N. SINGH and K. S. BOPARAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 1143.
2. F. CRITCHFIELD and J. B. JOHNSON, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 430.
3. J. V. KRISHNA REDDY and K. S. BOPARAI, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1975, **52**, 324.

An Electrochemical Technique for Preparation of Deionized Water

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IT was earlier reported by Palit¹ that electrolysis in W-tube cells results in formation of two sharp and static boundaries dividing the entire solution into three zones, viz., (i) cathodic alkaline, (ii) central neutral (water), and (iii) acidic anodic zones. A peculiar characteristic of the phenomenon is strong ion depletion in the central non-electrode zone. Later studies on theoretical aspects of this phenomenon² led to a deeper insight into the W-tube phenomena and experimental development of a much quicker method for producing the phenomenon, by induced ion-sweeping action of suitably added concentrated electrolytes (see Discussion). Further it has been recently reported by Palit that brisk ion-migration can occur even in trans-electrode regions during electrolysis³. Based on a combination of all these three principles we present here an